

Original Article

Comparative analysis of Syrian war (2011-2024) and Afghan war (1979-1989)

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Abstract

War is not a new phenomenon. It is evident in human history throughout the centuries. The Syrian war and the Afghan war were part of human history. Many studies are conducted on case studies, yet researchers pay less attention to studying them comparatively to find out similarities and differences between them. This paper aims to do a comparative study of the Syrian War (2011-2024) and the Afghan War (1979-1989) to discover their similarities and differences. Qualitative Comparative Analysis is used to conduct this research; to probe the similarities and differences between the case studies. The data sources are secondary data. The study is based on grounded theory by constant comparing of data throughout the study. Themes are developed to find similarities and differences. Both case studies have seemed entirely different in terms of the era, geographical locations, and type of government, yet many similarities co-exist between both cases.

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Introduction

By conquering Delhi and some areas of the Subcontinent, Afghanistan was curved out on the map of the world in mid-eighteen century, under guidance of Pashtun leader Ahmed Shah Durrani (1747-72). The territories of Afghanistan were transformed during a long process of diplomacy and war posed by the Great Game, a geopolitical rivalry between the interests of British and Russia. Three Anglo-Afghan wars waged in 1839-1842, 1878-1880 and in 1919. Afghanistan observed fierce events ranging from combats with superpowers, many destructive rebellions, and internal invasions by Amir Abdur Rahman Khan (1880–1901) to unify the country. After long struggles, Afghanistan became a buffer state between Russia and British that prevented foreign intervention from 1880 to 1901 in Afghanistan. It had a neutral stance during the Second World War under leadership of King Amanullah (1919-1929). Kabul was in a longest period of relatively peace and stability under King Zahir Shah (1933-1973) that was ended by bloodless coup in 1973 by Daoud Khan, who was cousin and brother-in-law of the king, which led instability in Afghanistan. In 1978, Daoud Khan was deposed by bloody coup of Afghan Communist Party (Byrd, 2012). A civil war started in the country when Communist of Afghanistan imposed radical reforms in 1979. Then communist government of Afghanistan requested to Soviet Union for intervention. Initially, the request was rejected by the USSR, but later on the Red Army intervened into Afghanistan on the occasion of Christmas in 1979 and stationed there over a period of a decade (Terry, 2011).

On the other hand, the today's Syria was once known as Great Syria, many times larger than present one. It was comprised of the region, which was divided by imperialist powers, that included today's territories of Jordan, Lebanon, Israel and Syria as well as the areas of southwest Turkey, West Bank and Gaza Strip. Before becoming a Mandate of Imperialist power, Syria was ruled by Ottoman Empire (Pipes, 1990). After

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the defeat of Ottoman Empire in the First World War and the victory of the British and France, Ottoman Empire was divided into fragments by the imperialists. The Levant (Bilad ash Sham) was divided between France and Britain as per Sykes-Picot Agreement (1916). However, in 1922 the Greater Lebanon identity was created by French and separated it from Bilad al Sham. On 17 April 1946, Syria got independence from France (Dostal, Ozdemir, & Imady, 2015).

Since 1946, many governments had changed in Syria, which labeled it as unstable state among the most unstable states in the world until Hafiz-ul-Assad came into power through coup (Rubin, 2008). Since 1970 the country was ruled by Hafiz-al-Assad till his death with irony hand and later on his son Bashir-al-Assad became the leader of the country. Although Hafiz-al-Assad successor was Basil-al-Assad, yet he died as result of an accident in 1994. The death of the elder brother Basil made the Bashir a new successor. He became new leader of Syria after death of his father Hafiz-al-Assad. He was highly educated and having familiarity with West; the Syrians hoped he would bring reforms in the country. He, however, encouraged the private sector and sold off many state-owned enterprises. He was appreciated by the West because of his neo-liberal reforms, but his reforms did not bring any changes in authoritative and centralized system of the state. The Arab Spring hit the Syria in March 2011 which posed a serious concern to Assad regime. Bashir ul Assad did some reforms, but that resulted in vain and did not prevent the Arab Spring to hold on Syrian territory (Erlich, 2014).

SYRIAN WAR

Arab Spring

In 2010, self-immolation of Mohamed Bouazizi in Tunis generated a spark of the Arab Spring. The death of the street merchant Bouazizi enlightened the people of Arab to raise their voices against their respective authoritarian regimes. The Arab Spring was against the long authoritarian regimes, yet there were many long-term factors: Economic factors which included unemployment, global crisis, inflation, poverty and economic inequality, that saliently existed in the MENA region; but the incident of Bouazozzi's suicide acted as fuel to fire. Economic Global crisis, moreover, occurred when Western states decreased the oil import. The food crisis occurred 2-3 years prior to the uprising and the inflation rate was reached to 25 to 30 percent in the affected states of the Arab spring. The unemployment and the education were also factors behind the spread of unrest among Arab peoples against their regimes. There was unemployment in youth in Morocco, Egypt and Tunis; particularly the female unemployment in the region also contributed to the uprising. The increase in education during last thirty years in the MENA region became one of the factors of the Arab spring because according to the modernization theory, it is believed that there is relationship between the education and the democratic process. Other factors which contributed to the unrest in the region were the political reforms desired by the people of the MENA region from their respective regimes, which were ignored by the rulers of the respective regimes. Last but not the least, social media played role in spreading of the uprising in Arab world (Mushtaq & Afzal, 2017).

Derra Uprising against the Assad regime

In March 2011, teenagers were arrested by the police on charges of wall-chalking anti-regime sentiments which included "Doctor, you are next" in a school; however, parents requested to different authorities for release their children, yet all had deaf ears to their request. The arrested kids were shifted to Damascus and tortured badly. The brutality by the regime on the opponents was not new measure, but the unexpected reaction of the parents was shocking in the form of a protest that started on 15 March outside Omari's Mosque. Regime forces opened fire on demonstrators that resulted in killing of four people. The following day, at the funeral of those children, a larger number of protesters against the regime raised anti-regime slogans, and the demonstration continued in meanwhile, so on 23 March, the regime forces surrounded the city, cut off the telephone, electricity supply and started a crackdown on the protestors (Philips, 2016).

The factors that caused the insurgency against the regime

The Arab Spring had its impact on Syria, where demonstrations started for governmental reforms. Many protestors were arrested and killed by Assad's forces during a demonstration against the regime. Opposition to the Assad regime emerged in the shape of the Free Syrian Army and the Syrian National

Council, which were carved out from the fragmentation of the national army. The conflict took the shape of war with the involvement of foreign actors and their assistance either to support the regime or the protestors. The situation worsened when the regime started oppressing insurgents by use of force and air strikes in 2012. The unsafe situation compelled the masses to leave the country and take refuge in their neighborhood states. Approximately 13.5 million Syrians sought asylum (Hulsman, 2017).

Syrian internal politics before the war

Unpopular policies by regime before uprising in accordance to regional changes

Bashar ul Assad became ruler in 2000. He introduced neo-liberal economic policies in the Syria which were acknowledged by elite class rather than poor class. These reforms were unpopular among large number of masses. Resultantly, Assad lost his support in the rural area as well as among labor groups. Demonstrations against Ba'th regime were not only because of Arab spring and Derra's barbarity but there were also grievances of people from being excluded from economic and political development of some areas; they were not happy with current secular laws. Inhabitants of Deraa were suffered from failed social market reforms, which was introduced by Assad, the aftermaths of the failed reforms led even to droughts. Masses of Baniyas town were conservative Sunni majority who were aggravated over laws relating to backlashing against Salafism and banned on face veiling of female teachers while in Homs these new laws seemed in favored and honored of Alawi emigrants (Philips, 2016).

Syrian war, supporters and opposition to the regime

The Syrian war was complicated in its nature because of a proxy war, which was similar in some ways to the Cold War fashion, because it became a game in which there were regional and global actors who played their roles for influence and strategic gains. There were two major groups in the Syrian war: one in support of the Syrian regime and the other in opposition to the Assad regime by siding with the insurgents. The Assad regime's well-wishers: Hezbollah and Iran were supporting the Assad regime; however, they were friends of the regime since 1980. Iran regarded Syria as a "one billion Dollar import credit line" and referred "senior Revolutionary Guard commanders" to Syria to contest with the rebels. Contrarily, Gulf Cooperation Council associates, the USA and Turkey supported the insurgent stance against the regime.

In short, Lebanese Hezbollah, Iran, and Russia, were supporters of the Assad regime, whose wish that Assad must remain in power. Russia desired to compete for power and influence against the USA in the region. On the other hand, the US disliked the Russian influence in the Middle East. Moscow tried several times to veto the humanitarian intervention in Syria in the United Nations Security Council against American interests (Hulsman, 2017).

USA's response to insurgents and its interests

Washington supported the rebels in the Syrian war. It had its interests for backing rebel group: firstly, from an ideological perspective of America, Syria was the only totalitarian regime, except Cuba and North Korea; Secondly, the Assad regime had aligned with Russia, which was regarded as a threat to the global hegemony of the USA; thirdly, a friendly government in Syria would be beneficial for the USA's geopolitical interests in the region and to its child Israel; Last, a desire for democratic government for the political and economic dominance (Berzins, 2013).

Russia's response to insurgents and its interests

Russia knew the worth of Syria in term of its strategic importance (Demir & Rijnoveanu, 2013). It supported the Assad regime rather than the rebels' groups. It had several interests in supporting the Assad regime rather than backing the opposition: Firstly, Russia had cordial ties with the Assad regime; Secondly, the Russia sacred of "Yugoslavization" of its own territories as Syria was seemed by Moscow as similar to that of Chechnya because of the reason that after fall of Assad who would stop extremists and its spill over its region, the North Caucasus (Berzins, 2013).

Results of the war

The Assad regime collapsed on 8th December 2024 that resulted in the abolishment of fifty year's old Assad regime (Hamdach, 2025).

AFGHAN WAR

Factors responsible for the uprising status of Afghanistan from 1978 to 1979

There were many factors which had an impact on the Afghan uprising against their communist rule. Firstly, the fragile government of Afghanistan was dependent on the Soviet for its foreign policy decisions. The Soviet-Sino conflict had an impact on Afghanistan. The People's democratic party of Afghanistan had a desire to have cordial relations with China, besides its loyalty towards the Soviet which could place a liability on the party to follow an independent foreign policy. Secondly, the change in the political weather of the region was the Iranian revolution which had a great effect on the Afghan people from a religious perspective that threatened to the communist regime (Haliday, 1980).

Afghanistan's internal politics that led to Soviet intervention

To understand the origin of the Soviet Afghan War, an overview of the internal politics of Afghanistan before the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan is necessary to mention. In April 1978, a communist group of Soviet trained, comprised of communist air force officers and army overthrew the regime of President Daoud. The coup resulted in the appointment of Nur Mohammed Taraki as President as well as Prime Minister, Hafizullah Amin as the foreign minister of Afghanistan and Babrak Karmal as deputy prime minister. All of the important figures were from the People's Democratic Party of Afghanistan (PDA) from both parts of the communist party. The Communist Party of Afghanistan was divided into two segments: Khalqi and Panchami. It was a risky situation to have two different sections of the party running the government, so it resulted in Karmal being posted to Czechoslovakia as a designated Ambassador of Afghanistan while other Parchami associates were sent to other countries as diplomats, which led to the domination of the Khalqi to run the internal affair of the country. The secret police of AGSA (Afghanistan Gatto Satoonkai Aidara: Department for Safeguarding the Interests of Afghanistan) was used to suppress opponents to the Khalqi regime. Pul-e Charkhi prison in Kabul was famous for the killing of people without a legal trial. The regime was not popular among masses because the regime had association with Marxist perspectives. The regime introduced reforms through decrees comprising increased women's rights like choice of marriage to women, co-education, elimination of bride price, compulsory schooling for girls as well as eradication of peasants' debts to landowners, which caused a restless in the conservative rural sector and resulted in resistance against the regime on religious grounds (Fremont-Barnes, 2012). These reforms were unpopular among the masses of Afghanistan. Only minority were in favors of regime that mostly included urban educational populations (Gibbs, 2006)

The peasant class had little support from the regime, but in particular, the workers and peasants rejected the Marxist ideology and provoked armed resistance. The lower-class personnel in the army left their units either to join the resistance or return home, taking their arms with them, but Taraki remained closely associate with Marxist ideology and strengthen his ties with the USSR by signing a treaty on 5 December 1978 for assistance of further military and economic aid from Soviet and 20 years of "friendship and co-operation" between two countries which was used by USSR as a justification for its intervention as per Article 4 of treaty cited in term of military co-operation. On 15 March 1979, a mass uprising was held against regime brutality in the western city of Herat. Most of the 17th Division joined the revolt, killing several Soviet advisors as well as government officials. The military occupied Herat and bombed the city and the rebels. Approximately 5,000 people were killed. The brutal approach of the regime further alienated many other soldiers from joining the rebellion movement, which decreased the army's strength to less than half its official strength of 90,000 personnel. The revolt in Herat accelerated an uprising spread across the country. The Soviet Union feared that any threat posed to Marxist ideology would threaten its hold on Eastern Europe. Any disturbance in Afghanistan would have direct influence on the USSR's Soviet integrity. The Soviet Union focused more on Afghanistan after the Herat uprising. Taraki was unable to control the internal situation of the country and repeatedly requested Soviet for its intervention to assist in maintaining the law-and-order situation in

Afghanistan, but the Soviets refused direct intervention in the internal affairs of Afghanistan to avoid further escalation of the situation. A violent coup by Amin, who ousted Taraki, changed the Soviet's perspective towards Afghanistan. Amin's rule increased the terror by AGSA (then called Khad (Khedamat-e Ettelaat-e Dawlati or State Intelligence Agency)). The Soviet got distanced itself from the Amin regime because of his brutality. Unfortunately, the U.S looked disapprovingly towards the Amin regime after February when Afghan security forces ruined a salvage attempt to rescue the USA ambassador in Kabul from unknown kidnappers. Furthermore, U.S attention from Kabul was diverted by the Iranian hostage crisis. In mid-1979, the Afghan economy worsened, and the rebels called Mujahideen became a source of the downfall of Amin's regime. KGB consultants visited the state to aware of the best way to safeguard a speedy subjection of the country with less interference from Afghan forces. Finally, Soviet Red Army invaded Afghanistan in December 1979 (Fremont-Barnes, 2012).

Unpopular reforms by regime of Afghanistan before war

The Communist came into power as a result of Saur revolution of 1978 which in turn posed revolutionary reforms in the country (Fremont-Barnes, 2012). The reforms brought by Communist Regime (the government People's Democratic Party of Afghanistan (PDPA) were not popular in large scale population of rural areas. The regime's reforms included prohibition of Bride price (a tradition in which family of bride has been paid in money), land reforms (certain limits of sixty hectares on a land to be kept per person holding and excess of certain limit would have divided in poor farmworkers) and literacy campaigning that also included women education. Co-education was promoted (Gibbs, 2006). Furthermore, the women were given rights even choice in marriage and compulsory education for girls (Fremont-Barnes, 2012).

The reforms made by the communist regime were caused unrest among the conservative masses which were inspired by the then recent Iranian revolution. There was resentment of these reforms among masses that made regime to use force (Fremont-Barnes, 2012).

Herat uprising against the regime

On 15 March 1979, an uprising began against the brutality of the regime in the form of a revolt in Herat (Fremont-Barnes, 2012). Herat was one of the provinces of Afghanistan in the western part of the country (Gibbs, 2006). The revolt resulted in the deaths of the Afghan officials and Soviet advisors. The regime in turn responded with harsh bombardment on the city that led to the killing of 5,000 people. The Herat rebellion was a triggering point in widening the opposition to the regime further to all corners of the country. The rebels wanted to overthrow the communist regime of the country and replace it with an Islamic one, as inspired by the Iranian Revolution (Fremont-Barnes, 2012). Most of the Afghan population was in favored of the revolutionaries who are known as Mujahideen by the West. Though there was a lack of organizational unity within insurgents, yet all of them were against the communist regime of Afghanistan, having extensive popular support of the population (Gibbs, 2006).

USA's response to insurgents in Afghanistan and its interests

The USA provided support to the rebels who were against the communist regime and the USSR's invasion of Afghanistan. The USA wanted to take revenge for its defeat in the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, backed by the USSR. The USA provided medical aid and radio to the Afghan insurgency (Imran & Xiaochuan, 2016). President Jimmy Carter of the USA retained an instruction allowing the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to provide support to the Afghan rebels, either in the form of economic aid or non-military supplies." Several months before the USSR, the CIA commenced secret assisting of the guerrillas after Carter signed the directive. The support of the USA to the insurgents was against the security interest of the USSR in the border region (Gibbs, 2006).

USSR's response to the insurgency in Afghanistan and its interests

Afghanistan was dependent on the Soviet Union (Collins, 2011). There were strong economic ties between the two countries. The USSR knew the importance of Afghanistan in terms of its own security interests: the biggest fear that Moscow had that West would establish Western bases in its neighborhood. Both countries shared some ethnic ties with the Uzbek and Tajik peoples of northern Afghanistan, with some ethnic

groups of the former Soviet Union, which led to the fear of internal treason against Soviet rule. USSR provided Afghan regime with economic and military aid as well as military training of its army men (Gibbs, 2006).

When the insurgency started in Afghanistan against the communist government, the Soviet Union ignored the request of help by the regime because it thought that its action would be against the people of Afghanistan, but after some time, when it became evident that support of the USSR was vital for the survival of the regime, so Soviet Union backed the communist regime of Afghanistan rather than the insurgents (Fremont-Barnes, 2012).

Afghan War: opposition and supporters of the regime

International Gravity

Afghanistan was a ground of international gravity by involvement of many actors in war besides its own people's opposition to the regime. Every state interfered in Afghan war. American involvement could be understood in context of revenge and defeat faced in Vietnam War backed by its cold war rival Soviet (Gates, 2006). Soviet intervened in Afghanistan in order to avoid the spread of insurgence to its own land (Fermont-Barnes, 2012). Pakistan seemed Soviet Afghan war a threat to Pakistan's security (Coll, 2004). China opposed Soviet intervention in Afghanistan publicly and view USSR actions as "Soviet causes belli, can fool no one" (Bradsher, 1985). China got involved in Afghan war secretly and to sell its cheap weapons in order to expend its market (Crile, 2003). India favored and supported the communist Afghan government and Soviet intervention in Afghanistan (Hameed, 2012). In short, Afghan war became a ground of international ground with all regional and international players having their interests to involve.

Two major alliance systems

Soviet Afghan war was bone of contention between two major powers. Many other countries got involve by supporting of the rebels against communist regime of Afghanistan and USSR. Afghan war was become international game and important role played by involvement superpowers as well as regional power. Afghan war led to the establishment of two alliance system. One in support of USSR interests in Afghanistan while other group (western alliance) in opposition of its interests (Imran & Xiaochuan , 2016).

End of war

Afghan war was concluded when the last soldier of Red army left on 15 February 1989; it was the result of Geneva accords. The withdrawal of the USSR red army did not bring political stability to the country because the Najibullah Regime's control was challenged by the rebel forces within the state (Fivecoat, 2012).

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE TWO CASE STUDIES

Similarities between both case studies

Similarities	Syrian war	Afghan war
Uprising against the regime	Derra uprising	Herat Uprising
Inspiration	Arab Spring	Islamic Revolution in Iran
International responses, the interests of the USA	The USA sided with the rebels to protect its interests in Syria, as the Assad regime was a threat to its interests as an ally of Russia.	The USA sided with the rebels because the rebels were against the communist regime of Afghanistan was an ally of the USSR.
International responses, the interests of the USSR/Russia.	Russia sided with the Assad Regime because it was an ally of Russia.	The USSR sided with the Afghan communist regime despite a popular uprising against the regime.
Internal politics before the war	Unpopular regime	Unpopular regime
International Gravity	Cold War	New cold war
Unpopular reforms before war	Assad regime made reforms which were unpopular among masses.	Communist regime of Afghanistan did reforms which were unpopular among the masses.

Authors’ assessment

Dissimilarities between the case studies

Dissimilarities	Syrian war	Afghan war
Location	Syria is one of the Middle Eastern countries.	Afghanistan is at the crossroads of Central and South Asia.
Timeline	The war of the 21 st century	War of the 20 th century
Regime	Hafizullah Assad established the regime in 1970, and in 2000, Bashar Assad became ruler and continued till 2024.	The Afghan communist regime gained control in Afghanistan in 1978.
Duration of war	(2011-2024) Thirteen year	(1979-1989) nine years
Type of war	Proxy war	Proxy war and direct Intervention by the USSR.

Authors’ assessment

CONCLUSION

To conclude, this study is based on the comparative study of two cases: Syrian and Afghan wars, and the use of grounded theory. Themes are developed to study the similarities and differences in both cases. Both are entirely different case studies based on the time framework, direct and indirect intervention and duration of war. Yet both cases have similarities. The comparison depicts that regional changes have an impact on political unstable state where the government is unpopular as seemed in both Afghanistan and Syria resulted in the uprising of masses against their respective regimes. The unpopular regimes who had made unpopular reforms in states against the wills of the majority masses led toward uprisings. Moreover, wars become a playground for many actors to play their role according to their national interests either by supporting the regime or rebel groups. The USA and USSR/Russia never miss an opportunity to play their cold war in a conflict whether it was Afghan war or Syrian war. Both were struggling and are still struggling to dominate the regions according to their interests respectively. In both cases, the Moscow’s interest was to support the regimes while the USA’s interest was to support the masses of the lands. Thus, the study finds that when there is uprising against unpopular regime based on the internal politics of the state especially when unpopular reforms which are less popular among majority of the state as well as the impact of regional changes lead toward political revolt against the regime. The insurgents or regime can be supported by different actors according to the actors’ interests in the conflict; whether it is a proxy war or direct intervention, many actors would play their role as per according to their national interests

References

- Bērziņš, J. (2013). *Civil War in Syria: Origins, Dynamics, and Possible Solutions*. National Defence Academy of Latvia, Center for Defence and Strategic Research.
- Bradsher, H. S. (1983). *Afghanistan and the Soviet Union*. Duke University Press. <https://archive.org/details/afghanistansovie00henr>
- Coll, S. (2004). *Ghost Wars: The Secret History of the CIA, Afghanistan and Bin Laden, from the Soviet Invasion to September 10, 2001*. The Penguin Press.
- Crile, G. (2003). *Charlie Wilson's War: The Extraordinary Story of How the Wildest Man in Congress and a Rogue CIA Agent Changed the History of Our Times*. Grove Press. https://books.google.com/books/about/Charlie_Wilson_s_War.html?id=nTtnBA1gbTcC
- Dostal, J. M., Ozdemir, O., & Imady, O. (2015, November 12). *Roots & consequences: Further explorations into the Syrian uprising*. The Centre for Syrian Studies (CSS), University of St Andrews, 7(4).
- Erlich, R. (2014). *Inside Syria: The Backstory of Their Civil War and What the World Can Expect*. Prometheus Books. https://archive.org/details/isbn_2901616149481
- Fivecoat, D. G. (2012). *Leaving the graveyard: The Soviet Union's withdrawal from Afghanistan*. *Parameters*, 42(2). <https://press.armywarcollege.edu/parameters/vol42/iss2/3>
- Fremont-Barnes, G. (2012). *Essential Histories: The Soviet–Afghan War 1979–89*. Osprey Publishing.
- Gates, R. M. (2007). *From the Shadows: The Ultimate Insider's Story of Five Presidents and How They Won the Cold War*. Simon & Schuster. <https://www.simonandschuster.com/books/From-the-Shadows/Robert-M-Gates/9781416543367>
- Gibbs, D. N. (2006). *Reassessing Soviet motives for invading Afghanistan: A declassified history*. *Critical Asian Studies*, 38(2), 239-263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14672710600671228>
- Halliday, F. (1980). *War and revolution in Afghanistan*. *New Left Review*, 115(2). <http://www.platypus1917.org/wp-content/uploads/readings/hallidayfred>
- Hameed, S. (2012). *Prospects for Indian and Pakistani cooperation in Afghanistan*. Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). https://csis-prod.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/legacy_files/files/publication/120823_Hameed_ProspectsIndianPakistan_Web.pdf
- Hulsman, M. S. J. (2017). *Humanitarian aid and peace prospects: Are the effects more adverse in proxy civil wars than in non-proxy civil wars? Case studies of Syria, Vietnam, and Afghanistan* (Master's thesis). Leiden University. <https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/bitstream/handle/1887/51928/Hulsman%20M.S.J.%20final%20MA%20thesis.pdf?sequence=1>
- Imran, A., & Xiaochuan, D. (2016, June). *The hidden hands: Soviet-Afghan War 1979-89, U.S. policy, and external actors*. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 6(6), 143-158.
- International Crisis Group. (2013). *Blurring the borders: Syrians spillover risks for Turkey*. <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/163955/225-blurring-the-borders-syrian-spillover-risks-for-turkey.pdf>
- Terry, P. C. R. (2011). *Afghanistan's civil war (1979–1989): Illegal and failed foreign interventions*. *Polish Yearbook of International Law*, 31, 209–234